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**Young Voices on Buddhism: A Survey of Contemporary Perspectives in
Taungoo District**

Presenter

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Abstract

This paper is an attempt to explore the connection between Buddhism and young people in Taungoo district. The primary objective of this article are to to measure Buddhist engagements in their daily lives, and the role of monastic institutions from a youth perspective. This paper also aims to identify challenges and opportunities for enhancing the flourishing of Buddhism among younger generation. A qualitative research methodology was applied, collecting data from the teenagers living in the Taungoo District. This study found that young Buddhists in Taungoo area maintain a strong engagement with Buddhism while their daily religious practices rely heavily on their habits and convenience of doing. Another significant finding is that Buddhist monasteries are changing into an event space where crowds gather for traditional ceremonies and cultural exchange. Furthermore, this research reveals the rapid development of social media platforms and attention economy as both opportunities and challenges for Buddhist missionaries.

Keyword: *Buddhist engagements, Youth, Monasteries, Challenges and Opportunities*

Introduction

In Myanmar, it has been over a decade that youth disengagement with religion rose concerns that today young people are becoming stray far from Buddhism. It is said that today young people came to believe Buddhism that is just accepted by tradition, lacking their own spiritual believes.¹ These kinds of view question of how to bridge traditional Buddhism with modern needs.

It is must be accepted that daily engagements, such as how many times one pay homage to the Buddha, are not perfect measures to determine one's own religiosity. Youth and Civic Engagement Survey carried out by *ISEAS – Yusof Ishak Institute* revealed that the Buddhist youth are less engaged in religious observances compared to the youth of other religions ([Anamwathana 2025](#)). However, the researcher noted that it was because Buddhism has no specific regulation on how many times a follower has to pray per a day, and today young Buddhists do not stray far from temple since the study showed a moderate level of religious engagement compared to peers of other faiths. However, rite and ritual are expressions of their faith devoted to the religion, and the personality reflected in their spirituality.

Recognizing the pivotal role of youth engagement with Buddhism, this article is designed to investigate the extent to which young Buddhist in Taungoo District engage with Buddhism. Here, the main objectives of this paper are to seeks the youth engagement with

1. U Htun, "Youth and Religion", uhtungoldsmith, Feb, 15. 2025, <https://www.uhtungoldsmith.com/youthandreligion/>

Buddhism and the role of Buddhist temples and monasteries. Furthermore, this paper also aims to anticipate the opportunities and challenges that are waiting for the development of Buddhism.

Methodology

It was decided that the most appropriate method to adopt for this investigation was to employed quantitative methodology. This method offers an effective way of describing frequency distributions within the dataset collected from the field research. Eighty-two students aged fourteen to eighteen, studying in Grade 7 through 11 were recruited for this study. The average age of participants was 15.225, with the majority being 15. [see Table 1.] The participants were divided into two group based on rural and urban area of Taungoo District. Although this sample size cannot represent the entire national population, the insights and feedback gathered from the participant were truly invaluable.

Table 1: Age Distribution

<i>Mean</i>	15.225
<i>Median</i>	15
<i>Mode</i>	15

Previous Researches on the Topic

However, several studies indicate that the youth engagements with Buddhism in these days challenges to the traditional monastic system. For example, young Buddhists in China widely practice Buddhist teaching as a way to emotional regulation, moral guide, stress alleviation, often through digital rituals, smartphone apps, and social media (Ouyang and Xie 2025). Davie used phrases like “Spiritual but not religious” and “Believing without belonging”, to refer people who have dropped out of formal religion, but adhere to non-institutionalized spirituality, pursuing ethical and psychological guidance of a religion (Davie 2007). These studies demonstrate that young people see religion as a tool to help their lives comfort, while resisting to affiliate with traditional religion, highlighting the new opportunities and challenges that are expected to be faced in the chapter of Buddhist missionary.

Daily Engagements of Young Buddhists

A careful analysis of survey data suggests that today young people in Taungoo district are not completely disconnected from Buddhism in contrast to allegations that they have strayed from Buddhism. When it comes to daily engagement of young Buddhists with Buddhism, the majority of participants, that is 60% of sample size, admitted to having a habit of daily prayer or paying homage to the Buddha, while only a small number of respondents, that is 40%, stated that they did not take part in daily prayer practice. [see Table 2.] These

results suggest the fact that today young Buddhist are becoming astray from the Buddhism turn out to be misinformation. However, the responses to the question about the reasons why they indulge in the daily practice is more interesting. Therefore, let us see the motivation driven them to pay homage to the Buddha every day.

Table 2: Daily Prayer Practice Involvement

<i>Age</i>	Yes	No
18	2	1
17	4	4
16	10	8
15	16	11
14	17	8
13	1	
<i>Total</i>	50 (60%)	32 (40%)

A considerable portion of responses to the question about the reason why they perform daily prayer is neither based on their belief nor the mental calmness gained during the prayer. Because when asked about the things encouraged them to pray every day, twenty-seven participants, that is 54% of sample size who pray every day, were unanimous in the view that they pay homage to the Buddha by virtue of their habit. Only nine students answered that they were encouraged by the parents to do so. [see table 3.] On the contrary, when asked about the things prevented daily ritual involvement, they did not respond like they do not believe in daily ritual such as paying homage to the Buddha. 56% of the students who do not practice daily ritual said that it was just because of their forgetfulness and busy school schedules. [see table 4.] On the whole, these results suggest an association between today young people and Buddhism. It seems safe to draw a conclusion here that these data reflect the lifestyle of teenagers lived in an era of constant notification buzzing on the social media rather than a negative attitude towards religion, which means they are not losing faith in religion, but awareness and attention.

Table 3: Motivation for Daily Prayer

<i>Age</i>	Offering alms-food	Being encouraged by parents	Being habitual	Others
18	1		1	
17	1	2	1	
16	3	1	6	
15	3	1	8	4
14	1	5	10	1
13			1	
<i>Total</i>	9	9	27	5

Table 4: Barriers to Daily Homage

Age	Busy schedule	Schoolwork	Don't know how to pray	Being forgetful	Other
18				1	
17		2		2	
16	1	2		4	1
15		2		8	1
14		2	1	3	2
13					
Total	1	8	1	18	4

The dataset demonstrating the rites and rituals performed at home further support the view that young Buddhist are losing attention, not faith. When asked about religious observances that had been accustomed to be done at home, 62% of the participants ticked off the option of praying or paying homage to the Buddha. This was followed by the option of giving alms-food and offering, chosen by 48 (58%) out of 82 students. A careful study may notice that these options are more convenient to perform at home than meditation and reading Dhamma book which demand a focused attention and deep concentration. [see table 5]

Table 5: Common Merit Performed at Home

Give alms-food	48
Praying	51
Meditation	9
Reading Dhamma	11
Don't do	4
Others	5

The Role of Monasteries for Young Buddhists

This study shows that the role of monasteries and temples has changed for the young Buddhists. Even though they did not altogether lost contact with Buddhist temples and monasteries, Buddhist religious places have become event spaces where they gather for community affair. According to the survey results, when asked the last time they visited to the monasteries and temples, majority of the participants (42%) agreed that they had visited within the last month, and 41% had visited only seven days ago. They statistic indicates the connection between young Buddhists and sacred places. However, the next inquiry into the frequency of their visit within a typical week leads to the conclusion that the connection between young Buddhists and monastic institutions is not that much strong. Here, 36 out of 82 students, that is 53.7%, said they do not typically visit to the monasteries and temples, while the 35.8% of the respondents replied they go to the monasteries at least once a week. As a disclaimer, it is important to note that only 67 responses of 82 students were calculated for this question, since 15 responses were excluded due to their contradictory and inconsistent answers between the

fifth and sixth questions. [see table 6] Nevertheless, it is evident that the relationship between Buddhist institutions and today young followers seems not to be tight enough. It is no longer a place they go for their daily worship and rituals. So, what persuade young Buddhist adherents to come together at the monastery?

Table 6: Frequency of Typical Weekly Monastery Visits

Don't visit	36
Only one time	24
Two times	5
More than 3 times	2

The top reasons why young people gather at monasteries are ordination ceremony, Kathina ceremony and Dhamma talk held at monasteries. [see table 7] These ceremonies and festivals rarely took place, for example once or twice a year. Here, it is obvious that monasteries are no longer a place for seeking inner peace through meditation and worship, but it is becoming an event space where the crowd gather and celebrate a particular ceremony. This suggests the fact that, from the youth perspective, the role of monastic institutions has changed. Monasteries are becoming a center of religion and also for social and cultural exchange.

Table 7: Reasons for Visiting the Monastery (Multiple Responses allowed)

Kathina ceremony	32
Dhamma Talk	37
Ordination ceremony	48
Cultural skill event	31
To do service (veyyāvacca)	29
Others	13

Opportunities and Challenges

This research found the general consensus that young people are not interested in Buddhist teaching in opposition to the attitude of young Buddhist towards Buddhism. When asked if they were interested in learning Buddhism, 71 students, that is 86% of the whole respondents, said yes, whereas only 32% replied in negative. Here, a proper degree of their desire to dive into Buddhism can be found. So, what make them hesitate to learning Buddhist teachings?

The inquiry into what prevent young Buddhists from learning Buddhist highlighted the opportunities and challenges that today young generation are facing. The main reason what holdbacks them to learn Buddhism is not because they find Buddhist teachings to be boring and irrelevant with them, but because of excessive screen time and busy schedules. [see table 8] Here, this indicates the problem lies not in the content but in the distribution channels. They

did not see the Buddhist teaching to be boring and irrelevant. But they were just trap in the busy schedule and attention economy of social media.

Table 8: Barriers to Learning Dhamma (Multiple Responses Allowed)

Busy schedule	26
Find to be boring	-
Feel irrelevant with young people	2
Being distance from monastery	15
Due to the much screen time	29
Discouraged by parents	4
No interest	7
Others	8

What is more, the mainstream that helps the young closer to the teachings of the Buddhist teachings blend traditional and modern ways. Predictably, many learn from their parents and by engaging in religious ceremonies. [see table 9] Here, what should be noticed is that, just as young people are learning Buddhist teachings from traditional ways, they are learning and hearing Dhamma through social media platforms such as Facebook, TikTok and YouTube and etc. However, almost all participant skipped the option “learn from friends” which highlights students do not usually discuss or talk about Dhamma in their casual conversation.

Table 9: Means of Learning Dhamma (Multiple Responses Allowed)

Through social media platform (e.g., TikTok, Facebook, YouTube, etc.)	36
Have a talk with monks	41
Engaging in rituals and ceremonies	51
From parents	45
From friends	6
Reading books	40
Others	8

Conclusion

This study set out to access the importance of religious engagement among young Buddhists. An initial objective of this study is to identify to what extent today young Buddhists involve in daily rite and ritual performances. This study was also designed to determine the role Buddhist monasteries from a youth perspective and to outline opportunities and challenges for future missionaries.

The most obvious finding to emerge from the analysis is that Young Buddhists in the Taungoo District engage with religious rituals primarily based on conveniences and habit of doing. Here, the connected patterns between those who practice daily prayer and who do not practices is astounding. The young practiced daily prayer due to their habit of doing and those who do not practice also cite their habit of forgetfulness. Moreover, another key finding is the

transformation of monasteries into an event space for social and community gatherings during religious celebration. This finding was also reported by *Anamwathana* in the studies conducted by *ISEAS – Yusof Ishak Institute*, which reported that young Buddhists in Thailand occasionally engage in religious observances on auspicious days. Contrary to the expectation, this study confirmed that the primary barrier to learning Buddhist teachings for young Buddhists in Taungoo is not a lack of interest, but one surprising variable that was found to be significantly associated with this issue is that they were overwhelmed by the modern challenges that steal their attention, such as screen times and school related works.

Here, the findings of this study suggest that the challenges are not what can be done to young Buddhists in order to feel Buddhist teaching are relevant to them, but rather determining how to effectively deliver Buddhist teachings to the young. Here, the fact that 43.9% of respondents learn Dhamma through social media platforms indicates a great opportunity to be seized. Conversely, the considerable number who agreed that the thing that is holding back them to learn Dhamma is also much screen time demonstrates a major challenge that should not be neglected.

This research successfully identified key aspects of daily engagement of young Buddhist in Taungoo district, the evolving role of monasteries from a youth perspective, and pertinent opportunities and challenges. However, this study was limited to the Taungoo district. Therefore, the researcher encourages and call for further studies with larger, more considerable representative sample size for more accurate and generalizable insights.

Bibliography

Anamwathana, Panarat. 2025. "Examining Religious Engagement Among Thai Buddhist Undergraduates." 11 June.

Ouyang, Danna, and ingyi Xie. 2025. "Buddhism Without Belonging: Functional and Digital Forms of Religious Engagement Among Chinese Youth." *Religion* 16 (1180).

Davie, Grace. 2007. *Vicarious religion: A methodological challenge. In Everyday Religion: Observing Modern Religious Lives*. Oxford: Oxford University Press.

Appendix

Survey Questionnaires

This survey is conducted to examine people's perceptions of Buddhism in the contemporary era, to study the participation of young people in religious activities, and to explore the interactions between Buddhism and youth today. The personal information of all participants will be kept confidential and protected. Therefore, you may respond openly and honestly.

We kindly request that you answer all of the following questions.

1. Respondent's age and occupation: _____
2. Do you pray or pay homage to the Buddha every day?
 - Yes, I pray every day.
 - No, I do not pray every day.
3. If you do not pray every day, what is the reason? (You may choose more than one)
 - Busy and tired from work
 - Schoolwork responsibilities
 - Do not know how to pray
 - Forgetfulness
 - Other _____
4. If you pray every day, what is the reason? (You may choose more than one)
 - Encouraged by parents
 - It has become a habit
 - Offering alms, flowers, etc.
 - Other _____
5. When was the last time you visited a monastery?
 - Within the last 7 days
 - Within the last 1 month
 - Within the last 3 months
 - Other _____
6. How many times do you usually visit a monastery per week?
 - Do not visit
 - Once
 - Twice
 - More than three times

7. Why do you usually go to a monastery? (Multiple answers allowed)

- Kathina ceremony
- Dhamma talk
- Donation ceremony
- Cultural or moral training
- Voluntary service (veyyāvacca)
- Other _____

8. What kind of merit-making activities do you usually practice at home?

- Offering alms or flowers
- Praying
- Meditation
- Reading Dhamma books
- Do not practice merit-making
- Other _____

9. How do you usually learn or hear about the Dhamma? (Multiple answers allowed)

- Online platforms (Facebook, TikTok, YouTube, etc.)
- Talking with monks
- Attending religious ceremonies
- From parents
- From friends
- Reading books
- Other _____

10. Are you interested in learning about Buddhism?

- Yes
- No

11. If not interested, what are the reasons? (Multiple answers allowed)

- Busy schedule
- Find teachings boring
- Feel irrelevant to young people
- Monastery is far away
- Excessive phone and internet use
- Lack of parental encouragement
- Personal lack of interest
- Other _____